

нов: *Xenopsylla conformis*, *Ceratophyllus laeviceps kuzenkovi*, *C. laeviceps ellobii*, *Amphypsylla dumalis*, *Paradoxopsyllus kalabukhovi*, *Ophthalmopsylla kiritchenkoi*, *Frontopsylla wagneri* — выходцы из пустынь Центральной и Средней Азии. Остальные 22 вида, обитающие в полупустыне, относятся к горно-степным.

Пустынные блохи *Ceratophyllus laeviceps ellobii* и *C. l. kuzenkovi* проникают в горные степи южного Хангая (Альдерхан, высота 1800 м), однако на северном Хангае они отсутствуют. В альпийской зоне на Хангае распространены горно-степ-

А — схема вертикальной поясности растительного покрова на Хангае (по Юнатову): 1 — высокогорный пояс, 2 — горный лес, 3 — горные степи, 4 — горно-пустынные степи, 5 — солянковые пустыни и полупустыни; Б — распределение эколого-фаунистических комплексов блох: 6 — горно-степного, 7 — горно-лесного, 8 — пустынно-степного.

ные виды блох, но видовой состав их значительно беднее, чем в горной степи. Хангай препятствует распространению на север пустынных видов блох, но не задерживает распространение монгольских горно-степных форм благодаря смыканию степного и высокогорного поясов. Для блох Хангая характерно явление эвритопности, особенно для паразитов пищух и мелких мышевидных грызунов. Наиболее широко распространена *Amphypsylla primaris*, паразитирующая на многих горно-степных и полупустынных видах грызунов.

Таким образом, на Хангае засушливый климат Монголии и периодические засухи способствуют сближению высокогорной, степной и полупустынной фауны не только птиц и млекопитающих (Сушкин, 1925; Формозов, 1929; Тарасов, 1953; Банников, 1954), но и в еще большей степени их паразитов — блох.

EVOLUTION AND SYSTEM OF CHELICERATA

A. B. Lange — А. Б. Ланге

(Moscow State University, USSR)

A system becomes as natural as closely it reflects the evolution of concerned organisms. Our knowledge of chelicerate evolution is incomplete. Availability of palaeontological data has made it possible to have a more complete picture of the phylogeny of primary aquatic *Merostomata* and *Eurypterida* (Fedotov, 1925, 1966; Ivanov, 1933; Stermer, 1956, 1963; Beklemishev, 1952, 1964, and oth.). But it is not so in case of the land arachnids.

Comparative studies of *Chelicerata* lead to the following conclusions. *Chelicerata* had their origin in the water and only later they migrated to land, whereas the *Teiocerata* (*Branchiata*) evolved almost entirely in water and *Atelocerata* (*Tracheata*) entirely on land. The peculiar texture of the aquatic *Chelicerata* had formed in Cambrian—Silurian periods by means of transition from benthic saprophagous *Trilobitomorpha* to benthic predators. The shift to benthic predatory habit brought about the reduction of antennules and compound eyes, absence of the movable head and masticatory mandibles, presence of the grasping chelicerae, the differentiation of the other appendages to locomotor—masticatory and branchial organs, the standard tagmosis etc. Judging by their ontogenesis (embryonisation of anamorphosis to epimorphosis) the *Chelicerata* were finally prepared to leave the aquatic habitat for the land. Howe-

ver, their distribution on land was greatly limited by their organisation. Evolution of most of the orders stopped at the primitive stage of hydrophilous nocturnal predators, respiring by lungs or by poorly developed tracheae, represented by only a few species. Only the spiders (20,000 species) and mite-like arachnids (10,000 species) conquered wide land areas and evolved various forms. The evolutionary success of the spiders is due to the web, web activity and building instinct, whereas the mite-like arachnids flourished because of their small size and broad evolution of metamorphosis and organisation.

The transition to terrestrial life was accompanied by many changes in structure and development. More significant among these is specialisation of the mesosomatic extremities which in the land forms gave rise to 6 variants: praegenitalia, pectinal organs, lungs, spinnerets, coxal organs or atrophy. The differences between orders in segmental combinations of these variants is the direct evidence of their independent transition to the terrestrial life.

This fact, that was not taken into account earlier, is significant for natural classification (discrimination) of *Chelicerata* into orders on the one hand and for estimation of the whole complex of characters of the orders and their phylogenetic interrelations on the other. *Chelicerata* is divided into 14 recent and about 10 fossil orders, and division of *Pedipalpi* into three orders (Milot, 1942) and *Acarina* into three orders (Zakhvatkin, 1952) is essential for regularising the number of orders. Absence of palaeontological data about direct ancestors of arachnid orders makes it difficult to form the superorder complexes. The majority of these subdivisions, evidently, were already distinguished in the aquatic stage of their evolution. It is significant to note that availability of palaeontological data on *Scorpionida*, the only land order so far of which we have such data, showed that it has originated independently from the *Eurypterida*.

Appraising the available classifications of *Chelicerata* (Petrunkevitch, 1949; Zakhvatkin, 1952; Dubinin, 1959, and others) from the point of view given above we consider that the system of A. A. Zakhvatkin, accepted by V. N. Beklemishev (1952, 1966), more and less fully reflects the natural relations between orders. Comparative studies point out that the orders form a complex taxonomical continuum — an evidence of the deep rooted unity of *Chelicerata* as a class, and on the other hand some grouping within the limit of the class taken into account in the mentioned system.

However, a change of ranks of systematic groups within the limits of the class is necessary for a fuller reflection of the phylogenetic relations: *Xiphosura*, *Holactinochitinosi*, *Actinochaeta* and *Actinoderma* ought to be regarded as subclasses and the more close orders ought to be united in superorders, e. g. *Palpigradi* — *Acariformes* — *Pseudoscorpiones* or *Phalangiotarbi* — *Opiliones* — *Trigonotarbi* — *Parasitiformes* and others. The independent migration of the various *Chelicerata* to land habitat and the great uniqueness of the arachnid orders will, with progress of knowledge, probably make it necessary to increase the number of subclasses.

LA TAXONOMIE DU GENRE *SARCOPHAGA* MEIGEN (DIPTERA, SARCOPHAGIDAE)

A. Z. Lehrer

(Iasi, Roumanie)

La nécessité de la révision des rangs taxonomiques des formes biologiques du genre *Sarcophaga* Meigen est déterminée par la description relativement récente de quelques espèces affines, comme par les recherches plus amples de la dernière décennie, effectuées dans plusieurs pays de l'Europe, sur la dispersion géographique, l'écologie et — dans une certaine mesure — sur la structure populationnelle de celles-ci.

Ces faits ont subminé la conception adoptée de longtemps, que le genre *Sarcophaga* comprend seulement 2—3 espèces, concretisées par quelques sous-espèces, mais ils ont fait lieu aussi à l'apparition d'une tendance de négation totale de la validité de la plupart de ces dernières (Gregor et Povolny, 1961).

Suite à ses recherches sur un grand nombre d'exemplaires, recoltés sur le territoire de la Roumanie, l'auteur a tiré la conclusion que la difficulté de préciser le rang taxonomique des formes de *Sarcophaga* est dû avant toute chose à l'imperfection de leur connaissance. Etant bien caractérisées de point de vue morphologique, surtout par les armatures génitales mâles, pouvant coexister dans le même biotope ou station, mais sans ressembler de formes intermédiaires, elles ne peuvent pas être considérées comme groupes allopatrices ou sympatrics de quelques espèces polymorphes, d'autant moins comme variations individuelles. Elles doivent être conçues seulement comme bonnes espèces, qui se groupent d'après les caractères morpho-structuraux en six sous-